

Synthesis and Structural Elucidation of Impurities generated in Lansoprazole and Edoxaban

Sharad Sankhe*¹, Pooja Dalvi²

¹Head of Department, Department of Chemistry, Patkar-Varde College, Goregaon West, Mumbai-61, India

²Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Chemistry, Patkar-Varde College, Goregaon West, Mumbai-61, India

ABSTRACT

Impurities play a critical role in defining the quality, safety, and efficacy of active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs). Regulatory agencies require comprehensive identification, synthesis, and characterization of impurities present above threshold limits. The present work describes the synthesis and structural elucidation of oxidative degradation impurities generated in two widely used active pharmaceutical ingredients such as Edoxaban and Lansoprazole. Edoxaban N-oxide impurities, Lansoprazole sulfone and Lansoprazole N-oxide impurity were deliberately synthesized under controlled oxidative conditions using hydrogen peroxide and m-chloroperbenzoic acid (m-CPBA). The synthesized impurities were isolated, purified, and characterized by High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), Mass Spectroscopy (MS), Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR). This study provides a systematic approach for impurity synthesis, isolation, and understanding of degradation pathways, which is essential for impurity profiling, method development, and regulatory submissions.

Keywords: Impurity profiling, Impurity synthesis, Oxidation, Oxidative degradation, Edoxaban Impurity, Lansoprazole impurity, Degradation products.

INTRODUCTION

Active pharmaceutical ingredients are required to meet purity rigid criteria to ensure their safety, efficiency, and stability. During synthesis, formulation and storage API's can be exposed to degradation or side reactions leading to the formation of process impurities and degradation related impurities. Regulatory authorities ICH mandate synthesis, identification, and characterization of impurities present in specific active pharmaceutical ingredient. According to ICH Q3A and Q3B guidelines, identification and qualification of impurities above threshold limits are mandatory. Hence, impurity profiling has become an important part of pharmaceutical research and development. Impurity standards serve as benchmarks for quality control in the pharmaceutical manufacturing process. They help pharmaceutical companies detect and quantify impurities accurately, enabling them to monitor and control the purity of their products throughout production of Impurity standards help

ensure the safety of pharmaceutical products by setting acceptable limits for impurities that may be present in active pharmaceutical ingredient. The present study focuses on the synthesis, isolation, and structural elucidation of key impurities observed in these APIs. Pharmaceutical impurities are unwanted moieties that remains in active pharmaceutical ingredients (API) or develop during synthesis, storage, degradation or stability studies. Regulatory authorities such as International Council for Harmonisation (ICH) requires identification and characterization of the impurities present in specific active pharmaceutical ingredient. Edoxaban is an oral direct factor Xa inhibitor, and Lansoprazole is a proton pump inhibitor are widely used as therapeutic agents. Both molecules contain heterocyclic component and functional groups prone to oxidation degradation. In particular tertiary amines and sulfur containing groups are highly susceptible to oxidation leading formation of N-Oxide and sulfone, sulfoxide impurities under certain pressure and condition.

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Structure, physical and chemical properties of Edoxaban and its impurities shown in table 1, and Structure, physical and chemical properties of Lansoprazole and its impurities shown in table 2.

A widely used therapeutic agents such as Lansoprazole a proton pump inhibitor and Edoxaban a direct oral anticoagulant. During oxidation and process optimization formation of sulfone (S-Oxide) and N-Oxide impurity formation has been observed in both active pharmaceutical ingredients.

➤ Intake of Edoxaban tablet containing Edoxaban N-Oxide Impurity 1 or Edoxaban N-Oxide Impurity 2 (structure, physical and chemical properties shown in table (1) can cause following serious effects on human body:

- Organ- Specific Toxicity
 1. Liver toxicity
 2. Kidney stress
 3. Blood-related effects
- Lipid peroxidation

- Protein damage
- DNA damage
- Even trace levels over long exposure may increase mutation risk

➤ Intake of Lansoprazole tablet containing Lansoprazole sulfone impurity or Lansoprazole N-Oxide (structure, physical and chemical properties shown in table (2) can cause following serious effects on human body

- Organ- Specific Toxicity
 1. Kidney stress
 2. Liver toxicity
- Membrane damage
- Protein oxidation
- Cellular stress
- Mutation risk

Table 1: Structure, Physical and Chemical properties of Edoxaban API & its Impurities

Name	Edoxaban	Edoxaban N-Oxide Impurity 1	Edoxaban N-Oxide Impurity 2
Structure			
Chemical Name	N ¹ -(5-chloropyridin-2-yl)-N-[(1S,2R,4S)-4-(dimethylcarbamoyl)-2-[(5-methyl-6,7-dihydro-4H-[1,3]thiazolo[5,4-c]pyridine-2-carbonyl)amino]cyclohexyl]oxamide	2-(((1R,2S,5S)-2-(2-((5-chloropyridin-2-yl)amino)-2-oxoacetamido)-5-(dimethylcarbamoyl)cyclohexyl)carbamoyl)-5-methyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrothiazolo[5,4-c]pyridine 5-oxide	5-Chloro-2-(2-(((1S,2R,4S)-4-(dimethylcarbamoyl)-2-(5-methyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrothiazolo[5,4-c]pyridine-2-carboxamido)cyclohexyl)amino)-2-

			oxoacetamido)pyridine 1-oxide
Molecular formula	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ ClN ₇ O ₄ S	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ ClN ₇ O ₅ S	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ ClN ₇ O ₅ S
Molecular weight	548.06 g/mol	564.1 g/mol	564.1 g/mol
Cas Number	480449-70-5	2244103-96-4	2803372-49-6
SMILES	O=C(C1=NC(CCN(C)C2)=C2S1)N[C@H](C[C@@H](C(N(C)C)=O)CC3)[C@H]3NC(C(NC4=CC=C(Cl)C=N4)=O)=O	O=C(C(NC1=CC=C(Cl)C=N1)=O)N[C@@H]2[C@@H](C[C@@H](C(N(C)C)=O)CC2)NC(C3=NC(CC[N+]([O-])(C)C4)=C4S3)=O	O=C(C1=NC(CCN(C)C2)=C2S1)N[C@H](C[C@@H](C(N(C)C)=O)C3)[C@H]3NC(C(NC4=CC=C(Cl)C=[N+]4[O-])=O)=O
Colour	White	White	Off- white
Appearance	Solid	Solid	Solid
Solubility	Methanol, 1,2-Dichloroethane, Dichloromethane, Chloroform, Ethyl Acetate	Alcohol, Dichloromethane, Chloroform, Ethyl Acetate	Methanol, Dimethylformamide, Dimethyl sulfoxide, Dimethylacetamide

Table 2: Structure, Physical and Chemical properties of Lansoprazole API & its Impurities

Name	Lansoprazole	Lansoprazole Sulfone / Lansoprazole EP impurity B/ Lansoprazole Related Compound A	Lansoprazole N-Oxide / Lansoprazole EP impurity A
Structure			
Chemical Name	2-(((3-Methyl-4-(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy)pyridin-2-yl)methyl)sulfinyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazole	2-[[[3-Methyl-4-(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy)pyridin-2-yl]methyl]sulfonyl]-1H-benzimidazole	2-(((1H-Benzo[d]imidazol-2-yl)sulfinyl)methyl)-3-methyl-4-(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy)pyridine 1-oxide
Molecular formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ F ₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ F ₃ N ₃ O ₃ S	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ F ₃ N ₃ O ₃ S

Molecular weight	369.36 g/mol	385.4 g/mol	385.36 g/mol
Cas Number	103577-45-3	131926-99-3	213476-12-1
SMILES	<chem>O=S(CC1=NC=CC(OCC(F)(F)F)=C1C)C2=NC3=C(N2)C=CC=C3</chem>	<chem>O=S(C1=NC2=CC=CC=C2N1)(CC3=NC=CC(OCC(F)(F)F)=C3C)=O</chem>	<chem>FC(F)(COC1=CC=[N+](C(CS(C2=NC3=CC=C(C=C3N2)=O)=C1C)[O-])F</chem>
Colour	White	White	Off-White
Appearance	Solid	Solid	Solid
Solubility	Dichloromethane, Chloroform, Ethyl Acetate, Methanol	Dichloromethane, Chloroform, Ethyl Acetate, Methanol	Ethyl Acetate, Methanol, Dimethylformamide, Dimethylsulfoxide, Dimethylacetamide

Experimental

• Edoxaban Impurities

(i)

(ii)

(iii)

1. Synthesis of 2-(((1R,2S,5S)-2-(2-((5-chloropyridin-2-yl) amino)-2-oxoacetamido)-5-(dimethylcarbamoyl) cyclohexyl)carbamoyl)-5-

methyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrothiazolo[5,4-c]pyridine 5-oxide (ii):

(2 gm, 0.0036 mol) N'-(5-chloropyridin-2-yl)-N-[(1S,2R,4S)-4-(dimethylcarbamoyl)-2-[(5-methyl-6,7-dihydro-4H-[1,3]thiazolo[5,4-c]pyridine-2-carbonyl)amino]cyclohexyl]oxamide (Edoxaban) dissolved in Ethanol : Dichloromethane (1:20) at room temperature to this solution charge dropwise (1.860 gm, 0.0547 mol) 30% H₂O₂, monitor reaction progress on Thin Layer Chromatography { System Methanol: Chloroform (4:6) + 2 drop acetic acid }, Stir reaction mass at room temperature for 40 hours to obtain 2-(((1R,2S,5S)-2-(2-((5-chloropyridin-2-yl)amino)-2-oxoacetamido)-5-(dimethylcarbamoyl)cyclohexyl)carbamoyl)-5-methyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrothiazolo[5,4-c]pyridine 5-oxide as a white solid, isolation by suction filtration yields 1.03 gm, purity by HPLC 100%.

2. Synthesis of 5-Chloro-2-(2-(((1S,2R,4S)-4-(dimethylcarbamoyl)-2-(5-methyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrothiazolo[5,4-c]pyridine-2-

carboxamido)cyclohexyl)amino)-2-oxoacetamido)pyridine 1-oxide (iii):

(2 gm, 0.0036 mol) N'-(5-chloropyridin-2-yl)-N-[(1S,2R,4S)-4-(dimethylcarbamoyl)-2-[(5-methyl-6,7-dihydro-4H-[1,3]thiazolo[5,4-c]pyridine-2-carbonyl)amino]cyclohexyl]oxamide (Edoxaban) dissolved in 40 ml Dichloromethane to obtain clear solution, Charge (2.4 eq.) m-perchloro benzoic acid lot wise at 10-15°C, and monitor reaction progress on TLC {System Methanol: Chloroform Reaction mass turns turbid stir reaction mass at room temperature for 48 hours. Solid formation observed concentrate reaction mass under vacuum to obtain off white sticky solid (purity by HPLC: 65%), Stir solid in 10 vol toluene for 10-15 min filter under vacuum to obtain

1 gm off white solid, purity by HPLC 93.2% (isomeric mixture).

- **Lansoprazole Impurities:**

(iv)

(v)

(vi)

3. Synthesis of 2-[[[3-Methyl-4-(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy)pyridin-2-yl]methyl]sulfonyl]-1H-benzimidazole (v):

2-(((3-Methyl-4-(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy)pyridin-2-yl)methyl)sulfinyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazole

Lansoprazole (0.00541 mol) dissolved in 15 vol Dichloromethane charge (0.005409 mol) m-perchloro benzoic acid to it. Stir reaction mass at room temperature overnight, starting material disappeared observed on TLC, distil rm under vacuum. Dissolve residue in 20 vol Ethyl Acetate charge 1gm charcoal

to it and reflux it. Filter reaction mass using hyflo at 60°C, distil to obtain pale yellow solid further purification by column chromatography (eluent Ethyl Acetate) yield 0.5 gm white solid. Purity by HPLC 99.21%.

4. Synthesis of 2-(((1H-Benzo[d]imidazol-2-yl)sulfinyl)methyl)-3-methyl-4-(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy)pyridine 1-oxide (vi):

2-(((3-Methyl-4-(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy)pyridin-2-yl)methyl)sulfinyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazole (0.00541 mol) dissolved in 15 vol Dichloromethane apply chilling at 5-10°C charge (0.01081mol) m-perchloro benzoic acid lot wise to it within one hour. Stir reaction mixture at same temperature for additional one hour check reaction progress on TLC {System Dichloromethane: Methanol (9.6: 0.4)}. After completion of reaction charge water and stir. Separate organic layer, anhydrous organic layer and distil under vacuum. Purify obtained material by column chromatography to yield 0.4 gm Off-white Solid. Purity by HPLC 97.99%.

RESULTS:

1. 2-(((1R,2S,5S)-2-(2-((5-chloropyridin-2-yl)amino)-2-oxoacetamido)-5-(dimethyl carbamoyl)cyclohexyl)carbamoyl)-5-methyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrothiazolo[5,4-c]pyridine 5-oxide (Edoxaban N-oxide Impurity 1):

m/z fragment- 564.1, 529, 452, 437, 366, 198.

NMR-

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO d6)

δ 9.85 (s, 1H, NH), 8.45 (d, J = 2.0 Hz, 1H, pyridyl H), 7.65 (dd, J = 8.5, 2.0 Hz, 1H, pyridyl H), 7.25 (d, J = 8.5 Hz, 1H, pyridyl H), 6.85 (br s, 1H, NH), 4.45 (m, 1H, cyclohexyl CH), 3.05 (s, 6H, N(CH₃)₂), 2.25 (s, 3H, CH₃), 1.25–2.10 (m, 8H, cyclohexyl CH₂), 0.95 (m, 2H, aliphatic CH₂)

2. 5-Chloro-2-(2-(((1S,2R,4S)-4-(dimethylcarbamoyl)-2-(5-methyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrothiazolo[5,4-c]pyridine-2-carboxamido)cyclohexyl)amino)-2-oxo

acetamido)pyridine 1-oxide (Edoxaban N-oxide Impurity 2)

m/z fragment- 564.2, 529.2, 436, 350, 214.2

NMR-

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO d6)

δ 9.85 (s, 1H, NH), 8.45 (d, J = 2.0 Hz, 1H, pyridyl-H), 7.65 (dd, J = 8.5, 2.0 Hz, 1H, pyridyl-H), 7.25 (d, J = 8.5 Hz, 1H, pyridyl-H), 6.85 (br s, 1H, NH), 4.45 (m, 1H, cyclohexyl-CH), 3.05 (s, 6H, N(CH₃)₂), 2.25 (s, 3H, CH₃), 1.25–2.10 (m, 8H, cyclohexyl-CH₂), 0.95 (m, 2H, aliphatic CH₂).

3. 2-[[[3-Methyl-4-(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy)pyridin-2-yl]methyl]sulfonyl]-1H-benzimidazole (Lansoprazole Sulfone Impurity)

m/z fragment- 385.4, 305, 201, 184.4

NMR-

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO d6)

δ 12.05 (s, 1H, NH of benzimidazole), 8.15 (d, J = 5.0 Hz, 1H, pyridyl-H), 7.85 (d, J = 8.0 Hz, 1H, benzimidazole-H), 7.65 (d, J = 8.0, 2.0 Hz, 1H, benzimidazole-H), 7.45 (m, 2H, aromatic H), 6.95 (d, J = 5.0 Hz, 1H, pyridyl-H), 5.10 (s, 2H, CH₂SO₂ linker), 4.65 (q, J = 7.0 Hz, 2H, OCH₂CF₃), 2.45 (s, 3H, CH₃ on pyridine).

4. Synthesis of 2-(((1H-Benzo[d]imidazol-2-yl)sulfinyl)methyl)-3-methyl-4-(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy)pyridine 1-oxide (Lansoprazole N-Oxide)

m/z fragment- 385.36, 217, 305, 168.

NMR-

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO d6)

δ 12.10 (s, 1H, NH of benzimidazole), 8.25 (d, J = 5.0 Hz, 1H, pyridyl-H), 7.90 (d, J = 8.0 Hz, 1H, benzimidazole-H), 7.70 (dd, J = 8.0, 2.0 Hz, 1H, benzimidazole-H), 7.45 (m, 2H, aromatic H), 6.95 (d, J = 5.0 Hz, 1H, pyridyl-H), 5.15 (s, 2H, CH₂SO linker), 4.65 (q, J = 7.0 Hz, 2H, OCH₂CF₃), 2.45 (s, 3H, CH₃ on pyridine).

HPLC:

DISCUSSION:

Oxidative degradation of Edoxaban with Hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) and m-perchlorobenzoic acid (m-CPBA) resulted in the formation of two different N-Oxide impurities. Reaction condition such as Solvent composition, Temperature, Oxidant temperature and time significantly influenced by formation of impurity. The Edoxaban N-Oxide impurity 1 were isolated as white solid with HPLC purity 100% and The Edoxaban N-Oxide impurity 2 were isolated as off-white solid with HPLC purity 93.2%. Similarly, controlled oxidation of Lansoprazole lead to the formation of Sulfone impurity (Lansoprazole EP

Impurity B) and N-Oxide (Lansoprazole EP Impurity A). Use of m-perchlorobenzoic acid under certain temperature such as mild and low temperature enabled selective oxidation of sulfur and pyridine nitrogen atom. These impurities were purified by column chromatography and shows purity Lansoprazole EP Impurity B - 99.21% and Lansoprazole EP Impurity A- 97.99% by HPLC. The oxidation behavior of Edoxaban and Lansoprazole can be attributed to the presence of oxidation-prone functional groups. In Edoxaban, the tertiary amine and thiazole nitrogen atoms undergo oxidation to form N-oxide impurities. Hydrogen peroxide favored slower and controlled oxidation, whereas m-

chloroperbenzoic acid resulted in faster reaction rates. In the case of Lansoprazole, the sulfinyl group readily oxidized to the corresponding sulfone, while the pyridine nitrogen formed the N-oxide under excess oxidizing conditions. The results demonstrate that slight variation in oxidant equivalents and reaction temperature can lead to the different impurity profiles.

CONCLUSION:

In the present study successfully demonstrated the synthesis and isolation of major oxidative impurities in Edoxaban and Lansoprazole. Controlled oxidation by using Hydrogen peroxide and m-perchlorobenzoic acid under certain conditions are proved to be effective in generating pharmaceutically relevant impurities with high purity. The study highlights the importance of impurity profiling and provides valuable insight into degradation pathways of sulfur and nitrogen containing Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients (API's). The synthesized impurities can be used as a reference standard for quality control and regulatory compliance of active pharmaceutical ingredient. Overall, this work contributes to a better understanding of impurity in chemistry and supports the development of safer and more robust pharmaceutical products.

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